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A Study to evaluate the level of knowledge related to the Basic Life Support module among fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students at Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam

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ABSTRACT

Basic Life Support (BLS) is a critical component in emergency care, enabling healthcare professionals to provide immediate assistance to individuals experiencing life-threatening conditions such as cardiac arrest and respiratory failure. Adequate knowledge of BLS among nursing students is essential, as they are often the first responders in clinical settings. This study was conducted to evaluate the level of knowledge related to the Basic Life Support module among fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students at Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam. A descriptive cross-sectional research design was adopted for the study. The sample consisted of fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students selected using a purposive sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire designed to assess the students' knowledge regarding various aspects of BLS, including airway management, chest compressions, rescue breathing, and emergency response protocols. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that a majority of the students possessed moderate knowledge regarding BLS, while a smaller proportion demonstrated adequate knowledge. However, certain gaps were identified in specific areas such as the correct sequence of resuscitation and compression-to-ventilation ratios. The study concludes that although nursing students have a basic understanding of BLS, there is a need for regular training sessions, workshops, and simulation-based learning to enhance their knowledge and skills. Continuous education and reinforcement of BLS

guidelines are recommended to ensure better preparedness in handling emergency situations.

Keywords: *Basic life support, knowledge, nursing students, emergency care, BLS training*

INTRODUCTION

Basic Life Support (BLS) refers to the early identification of life-threatening conditions and the immediate provision of measures to maintain breathing and blood circulation during cardiac or respiratory arrest[1]. It consists of essential life-saving techniques such as rescue breathing to assist ventilation and chest compressions to ensure adequate blood flow to the brain

and other vital organs. Adequate knowledge of BLS and the timely application of basic cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) techniques can sustain a patient's life until advanced medical care becomes available and, in certain situations, may be sufficient to achieve survival independently[2].

Historically, one of the earliest documented successes of artificial respiration using the mouth-to-mouth method was reported in 1744, when Tossach successfully revived a suffocated miner[3]. Since then, resuscitation practices have undergone significant refinement, leading to the development of structured protocols collectively referred to as cardiopulmonary resuscitation, commonly known today as Basic Life Support. Although CPR is a major component of BLS, the two terms are often used interchangeably despite BLS encompassing additional emergency interventions. Introduced in 1960, CPR is a simple yet highly effective technique that enables both trained professionals and laypersons to preserve life during the critical initial minutes following cardiac or respiratory arrest [4].

arrest accounting for a substantial proportion of these deaths. Without the prompt initiation of effective CPR, survival is unlikely. Recent evidence also emphasizes that the rapid response and skill level of the first responder play a crucial role in determining early survival outcomes following cardiac arrest [5].

A cross-sectional study conducted at Dow International Medical College, Karachi, assessed awareness of BLS among medical students using a structured questionnaire. Of the 61 participants, only 14.7% had received formal Basic Life Support (BLS) training, whereas the majority (85.3%) had never attended any such course, underscoring a substantial training gap.[6]

Basic Life Support is an indispensable competency for healthcare workers as well as the general public, as it enables effective action during medical emergencies. The present study sought to evaluate the knowledge and attitudes of

Coronary heart disease remains a leading cause of mortality worldwide, particularly in developing nations, with sudden cardiac

nursing students toward BLS techniques through a checklist-based demonstration approach. Conducted under the supervision of a certified American Heart Association (AHA) trainer, the program aimed to develop students' confidence and ability to independently perform CPR [7].

BLS forms a vital link in the chain of survival by reducing the likelihood of death following cardiac arrest and improving rates of hospital discharge. Several studies have reported inadequacies in CPR quality both in pre-hospital and in-hospital settings, which have prompted updates in recent BLS guidelines. In general, BLS refers to the immediate care delivered by first responders, healthcare providers, and trained public safety personnel to individuals experiencing cardiac arrest, respiratory failure, or

The heart plays a central role in sustaining life by facilitating oxygen delivery, nutrient transport, and immune function through the circulatory system. Lifestyle factors such as diet and physical activity significantly influence cardiovascular health. Each year, numerous individuals experience severe illnesses or accidents leading to respiratory arrest, a portion of which progress to cardiac arrest. In high-income countries, sudden cardiac arrest is among the leading causes of death [10]. Common triggers include myocardial infarction, drowning, choking, trauma, electrical injury, drug reactions, and severe allergic responses. CPR remains the most effective emergency intervention to improve survival in such cases, with BLS serving as the initial and most critical step in resuscitation [11].

airway obstruction. It includes procedures such as CPR, defibrillation, and basic first aid to maintain life until advanced medical treatment is available or the patient reaches a healthcare facility [8].

Earlier research has consistently shown that early recognition of cardiac arrest, prompt activation of emergency medical services, immediate initiation of CPR, and early defibrillation significantly improve survival outcomes. BLS is commonly provided in pre-hospital environments and does not usually involve invasive procedures or medication administration [9]. It can be effectively integrated with Advanced Life Support (ALS). With brief training programs, most laypersons are capable of acquiring and performing essential BLS skills.

Despite advances in resuscitation techniques, including automated external defibrillators (AEDs) and therapeutic hypothermia, survival rates following out-of-hospital cardiac arrest remain low, and many survivors experience long-term neurological impairment. Resuscitation following cardiac arrest also results in widespread ischemia-reperfusion injury affecting multiple organs, particularly the brain and heart [12].

Studies indicate that nurses generally demonstrate higher levels of BLS knowledge compared to nursing students, underscoring the importance of evaluating both theoretical understanding and practical skills to prevent avoidable disability or death due to delayed

resuscitation. Incorporating BLS training into the nursing curriculum is therefore essential. The timing of CPR is especially critical, as irreversible neuronal damage may begin within two minutes of cardiac arrest [13].

Globally, cardiovascular diseases account for approximately 30% of all deaths, with a disproportionately higher burden in developing countries. Sudden cardiac arrest accounts for nearly half of these fatalities, and survival rates in out-of-hospital settings remain low. [14]. Early use of AEDs has been shown to significantly increase survival, particularly in cases of ventricular fibrillation, which is a major cause of sudden cardiac death.

Although only a small proportion of the population receives CPR training annually, survival from sudden cardiac arrest largely depends on the immediate actions of bystanders, including early recognition, activation of emergency services, initiation of hands-only CPR, and timely use of an AED [15]. As CPR guidelines continue to evolve based on emerging scientific evidence, regular updates and retraining are essential to ensure optimal care. Learning CPR and maintaining proficiency in BLS empowers individuals to act decisively and save lives in emergency situations.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The objective of this study was to explore academic and demographic factors that influence the timely completion of a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSc Nursing) program. Completing the nursing curriculum within the prescribed duration

has implications not only for current and prospective students but also for healthcare institutions and the wider community. This quantitative, retrospective study aimed to identify evidence-based academic admission criteria that could assist in selecting nursing students who are more likely to successfully complete the program on schedule without academic failure. Demographic variables such as age, gender, ethnicity, and transfer student status were also examined to determine their association with timely program completion. Logistic regression and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analyses were employed to evaluate the relationship between timely completion and factors including pre-admission cumulative grade point average, science subject performance, and demographic characteristics [16].

Globally, cardiovascular disease contributes substantially to mortality, with Asian countries accounting for nearly 80% of related deaths. In India, cardiac arrest affects approximately 33%–44% of individuals both inside and outside hospital settings, of whom only 15%–25% survive following resuscitation. Delayed initiation of cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) and inadequate coronary and cerebral perfusion during resuscitation are major contributors to poor outcomes. According to the World Health Organization, India was projected to represent nearly 60% of the global cardiac patient population by 2020. Notably, close to half of all cardiovascular-related deaths in India occur before the age of 70, compared to approximately one-fifth in Western countries. In Karnataka, heart

disease affects about 10% of adults in urban areas and 5% in rural populations.

The American Heart Association (AHA) emphasizes that all healthcare professionals who have patient contact should undergo regular life-saving skills training. Numerous studies have demonstrated that effective cardiopulmonary resuscitation significantly improves survival and recovery outcomes. CPR should be administered to individuals who have a reasonable chance of survival or life prolongation. Consequently, Basic Life Support (BLS) training is essential for healthcare providers. Nurses, in particular, play a pivotal role within the healthcare system, and healthcare institutions must ensure the availability of structured and continuous BLS training programs to enhance nurses' knowledge, skills, and competencies [17].

The primary aim of this study was to assess the effectiveness of Basic Life Support (BLS) training among non-medical students by evaluating improvements in both their theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Cardiac diseases remain the leading cause of death worldwide, and sudden cardiac arrest requires immediate intervention across all age groups. Prompt management focusing on airway maintenance, breathing support, and circulation is critical for survival. CPR represents the initial and most vital intervention in the management of cardiac arrest. Healthcare professionals contribute significantly to reducing mortality by delivering timely and effective CPR at the site of arrest. The AHA consistently

underscores the urgent need for comprehensive CPR knowledge and skill competency among all healthcare workers to reduce preventable deaths [18].

Theoretical instruction alone is insufficient for mastering CPR, as it is a skill-based procedure that requires hands-on practice combined with cognitive understanding. Regular updates and refresher training are necessary to maintain healthcare professionals' confidence, technical proficiency, and clinical effectiveness. Evidence indicates that cardiac arrest poses a serious life-threatening condition regardless of age. A review of reported cardiac arrest cases between 2001 and 2019 revealed that among 377 documented incidents occurring both in-hospital and out-of-hospital, CPR was initiated in only a small number of cases, with survival noted in a limited proportion [19].

Early recognition of cardiac arrest and immediate initiation of CPR not only reduce adverse outcomes but also significantly enhance survival rates. Research further shows that survival following in-hospital CPR (22.3%–25.2%) is notably higher than out-of-hospital survival rates (approximately 10.8%), largely due to delays and inadequate CPR performance by first responders in community settings. Therefore, adequate knowledge and competent practice of CPR among healthcare professionals are critical determinants of patient survival following cardiac arrest[20].

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The primary goal of cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) is to maintain an artificial flow of oxygenated blood

throughout the body, particularly to the brain and heart, until normal cardiac and respiratory functions are restored. The findings of the present study revealed that the majority of participants demonstrated a moderate level of theoretical knowledge (64%) but inadequate practical skills (66%) related to Basic Life Support (BLS). Deficiencies in knowledge were particularly evident in critical aspects of CPR, including recognition of cardiac arrest signs, assessment of the carotid pulse, timely rotation of the compressor, correct hand placement for chest compressions, and indications for defibrillation. Practical performance was notably weak in areas such as activating emergency assistance, delivering high-quality CPR with appropriate compression rate and depth, ensuring full chest recoil, reassessing the pulse, and accurate placement of automated external defibrillator (AED) pads [21].

Basic Life Support encompasses a set of essential emergency interventions applied during life-threatening conditions such as cardiac arrest, respiratory compromise, and airway obstruction. It includes early CPR, airway maintenance, and prompt defibrillation. As future healthcare professionals, nursing students must acquire adequate knowledge and competency in these skills to respond effectively to emergency situations. This study underscores the need to enhance Basic Life Support (BLS) education and practical training among nursing students in order to improve patient outcomes during critical events.

Sudden cardiac arrest remains a major global health concern and is among the leading causes of mortality worldwide. A significant proportion of these events occur outside hospital settings, where survival is heavily dependent on immediate bystander intervention. Early initiation of effective BLS within the first few minutes has been shown to markedly increase survival rates. Nursing students frequently act as first responders in both hospital and community environments, making proficiency and confidence in BLS procedures essential[22].

During clinical postings, nursing students are often the first individuals to identify and respond to medical emergencies. Their ability to promptly initiate BLS can be decisive in saving lives. However, existing evidence indicates that many students lack sufficient knowledge and practical competence in BLS, emphasizing the need for systematic assessment and targeted skill enhancement to ensure preparedness in real-world situations.

Although BLS instruction is included in most nursing curricula, training is often predominantly theoretical, with limited opportunities for practical application. As a result, students may be unfamiliar with the correct sequence of BLS steps or may hesitate during actual emergencies. The present study aims to identify these gaps and advocate for a skill-oriented learning approach that integrates theory with repeated hands-on practice.

Well-trained nursing students are capable of initiating BLS promptly, thereby improving patient survival and minimizing

complications. The significance of this study lies in its potential to underscore the necessity for comprehensive and effective BLS training and to inform improvements in teaching methodologies within nursing education programs. Enhanced training ultimately contributes to improved emergency care delivery in both hospital and community settings [23].

The findings of this study may guide curriculum planners to strengthen or revise existing BLS training modules by incorporating simulation-based learning, regular competency assessments, and refresher courses. Modern educational strategies such as manikin-based practice and video-assisted instruction can further enhance skill retention and performance.

Additionally, the study aims to foster self-confidence among nursing students by ensuring they are adequately prepared to manage emergencies. Confidence plays a critical role in enabling prompt decision-making and effective action during life-threatening situations. Developing strong practical BLS competencies not only improves individual performance but also enhances the overall emergency response capacity of healthcare systems.

The outcomes of this research provide a foundation for future studies on BLS education, long-term retention of resuscitation skills, and the effectiveness of various training models. Furthermore, the findings may assist healthcare institutions in designing training programs,

certification courses, and awareness initiatives to promote BLS proficiency among students and the wider community [24].

In conclusion, this study highlights the urgent need to assess and enhance Basic Life Support knowledge and skills among nursing students. Addressing educational gaps, strengthening curricula, and building confidence are essential steps toward preparing competent healthcare professionals capable of saving lives during emergencies. This study contributes to improving emergency preparedness and patient safety within the healthcare system.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A descriptive study to evaluate the level of knowledge related to the Basic Life Support module among fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students at Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam

OBJECTIVES

- The objectives of the study are:
- To assess the level of knowledge regarding the Basic Life Support (BLS) module among fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students of Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam, Pathanamthitta District.
- To determine the association between the level of knowledge regarding the Basic Life Support (BLS) module and selected demographic variables among fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students.
- Fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students may possess a certain

ASSUMPTION

level of knowledge regarding Basic Life Support (BLS).

- Practical exposure and demonstration-based training in

HYPOTHESIS

There will be a statistically significant association between the level of knowledge regarding the Basic Life Support (BLS) module and selected demographic variables.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology provides a systematic framework for addressing research problems in a structured and scientific manner. It encompasses a sequence of well-defined steps, beginning with the identification of the research problem and extending to the analysis and interpretation of data leading to valid conclusions. This chapter outlines the

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design refers to the overall plan for addressing a research question, incorporating specific strategies to enhance the validity, reliability, and overall rigor of the study.

RESEARCH VARIABLES

Variables

Variables are attributes, characteristics, or qualities of individuals, objects, or situations that can change or vary during the course of a study.

Independent variable

SETTING OF THE STUDY

The setting refers to the physical location and contextual conditions under which data collection takes place. The present

Basic Life Support can enhance students' knowledge and understanding of BLS.

methodological procedures adopted for the collection, organization, and analysis of data in the present study.

The research approach employed is applied research, which focuses on evaluating how effectively a program, practice, procedure, or policy functions in real-world settings. The primary purpose of this approach is to assess or determine the effectiveness of an existing program. Accordingly, a quantitative research approach was selected for this study to objectively measure and analyze the outcomes.

The independent variable refers to the factor, activity, or intervention that is deliberately manipulated or controlled by the researcher in order to observe its effect on another variable.

Dependent variable

The dependent variable is the outcome or response that occurs as a result of changes in the independent variable and is the variable that the researcher seeks to explain or predict. In the present study, the dependent variable was the level of knowledge regarding Basic Life Support (BLS) among fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students.

study was carried out at Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam, Pathanamthitta District.

Population

The population is defined as the entire group of individuals or elements that share characteristics relevant to the study. The accessible population for the present research comprised fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students at Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam, Pathanamthitta District.

Sample

A sample is a subset of the population selected by the researcher from which data are collected to represent the entire population. In the present study, the sample consisted of fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students of Archana College of

Nursing, Pandalam, Pathanamthitta District.

Sample size

Sample size refers to the total number of participants selected from the population to obtain the required data for the study. In the present study, the sample comprised 40 fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students of Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam, Pathanamthitta District.

Sampling technique

The samples were selected using a purposive sampling technique from among fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students of Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam, Pathanamthitta District.

Inclusion Criteria

- Willing to participate in the study
- Present during data collection
- Cooperative and responding to the questions

Exclusion Criteria

- Not willing to participate
- Not accessible during data collection

TOOL / INSTRUMENTS

A research tool is an instrument or device employed to measure the concept of interest in a study and to systematically collect relevant data from the participants.

Description of the Tool

The final draft of the tool was prepared considering the suggestions of validators.

It comprises 2 sections:

Section A: Demographic variables.

Development / Selection of The tool

Prior to developing the research tool, a comprehensive review of relevant literature was conducted, including consultation of books and scholarly articles. Additionally, opinions and suggestions from experts in the field, along with the investigator's prior experience in the research area, were taken into consideration. Based on the objectives of the study, the investigator designed and selected an appropriate tool for data collection.

Section B: Structured knowledge questionnaire.

Section A: demographic data

This part of the tool consisted of socio demographic data which includes age, sex,

religion, educational status, occupation of parents.

Section B: structured questionnaire

To assess the knowledge regarding behavioral problems. It contains 30 multiple choice questions to assess knowledge of 4th Semester Bsc Nursing students regarding the knowledge of BLS . Each question has 4 options in which one option is correct and the other three options are wrong. Each correct answer carries one mark, the wrong answer carries a zero mark, the possible maximum mark is 30 and the minimum score is zero.

Tool Validity

Content validity

Content validity is the degree to which a research instrument effectively measures the concept it is designed to assess. To establish content validity, the tool was submitted to medical professionals trained in Basic Life Support (BLS) as well as experts from the Medical-Surgical department. All feedback and suggestions provided by the experts were carefully reviewed, and necessary modifications were made in consultation with the research guide.

Reliability

The reliability of the tool was assessed using the Brown–Spearman split-half method, which yielded a reliability coefficient of +0.98 for the knowledge questionnaire, indicating that the tool was highly reliable.

Data Collection Process

Data collection is the systematic and organized process of gathering information

relevant to the objectives, purpose, or hypotheses of a research study.

Phase-1

After getting approval from the concerned authority for the study, demographic data, questionnaire.

Phase 2

The study was carried out over a period of one week, from 16th June 2025 to 22nd June 2025. The researcher explained the purpose of the study to the participants in a clear and compassionate manner, and informed consent was obtained from all fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students. A total of 40 students were selected as the sample using a purposive sampling technique. The first phase of data collection was conducted on 16th June 2025 at Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam, with all 40 participants. The students' knowledge regarding Basic Life Support (BLS) was assessed using a structured questionnaire.

Plan for data analysis

The collected data were systematically organized, tabulated, and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Frequencies and percentages were calculated to summarize the demographic characteristics of the participants. The mean score, mean percentage, and standard deviation were computed to assess the pre-test and post-test knowledge levels. The Chi-square test was applied to determine the association between the participants' pre-test knowledge levels and selected demographic variables.

This chapter deals with the analysis and interpretation of the data collected to assess the knowledge regarding Basic Life Support (BLS) among 4th semester BSc Nursing students of Archana College of

Nursing, Pandalam. The data obtained were coded, tabulated, analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, and presented in tables and figures.

Section A: Distribution of Demographic Variables

Variable	Category (Code)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age	1	14	35.0
	2	26	65.0
Gender	Male (1)	11	27.5
	Female (2)	29	72.5
Previous Clinical Experience	Yes (1)	22	55.0
	No (2)	18	45.0
Prior BLS Training	None (1)	40	100
Academic Performance	Poor (1)	1	2.5
	Average (2)	8	20.0
	Good (3)	31	77.5
High School Type	Code 1	40	100
Exposure to Emergencies	Yes (1)	12	30.0
	No (2)	28	70.0
Access to BLS Resources	No (2)	40	100

Section B: Knowledge Level of Students

Interpretation: Majority of students (62.5%) had average knowledge regarding BLS, 35% had good knowledge, 2.5% had poor knowledge, and none reached excellent level.

Section C: Association between Knowledge and Demographic Variables

Interpretation: There was no statistically significant association between knowledge and demographic variables among the students.

RESULTS

The present study assessed the knowledge regarding BLS among 4th semester BSc Nursing students. The findings revealed that most students (62.5%) had average knowledge, 35% had good knowledge, and only one student had poor knowledge. None achieved excellent knowledge levels.

These results align with studies conducted by Bindhu & Lucas (2016) and Umran & Sarpkaya (2013), which also reported moderate levels of BLS knowledge among nursing students, emphasizing the need for repeated practice sessions and refresher training.

The absence of significant associations between demographic variables and knowledge suggests that factors like age, gender, or academic performance do not strongly influence BLS knowledge. Similar findings were observed by Karim & Yunus (2016).

The lack of prior BLS training among all students highlights a critical gap in formal certification and practical exposure, which may explain the predominance of 'average' knowledge levels.

Summary

The present descriptive study was conducted to assess the knowledge regarding the Basic Life Support (BLS)

module among fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students at Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam, Pathanamthitta District. The study aimed to evaluate the students' knowledge levels and to determine the association between their knowledge and selected demographic variables.

A total of 40 students were selected using purposive sampling. Data were collected over one week, from 16th June 2025 to 22nd June 2025. The researcher explained the purpose of the study, obtained informed consent, and assessed the participants' knowledge using a structured questionnaire.

The collected data were organized, tabulated, and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequencies and percentages were used to describe

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that fourth-semester B.Sc. Nursing students at Archana College of Nursing, Pandalam, possessed an overall average level of knowledge regarding the Basic Life Support (BLS) module. Significant gaps were identified in critical areas of CPR and emergency response, highlighting the need for enhanced practical training and repeated skill-based demonstrations. The findings

demographic variables, while mean scores, mean percentages, and standard deviations were calculated to analyze pre-test and post-test knowledge levels. The Chi-square test was applied to examine the association between knowledge levels and selected demographic variables.

The findings revealed that a majority of the students had an average level of knowledge regarding the BLS module, with gaps identified in critical areas such as recognition of cardiac arrest, carotid pulse assessment, chest compression techniques, and defibrillation. The study highlights the importance of structured BLS training and practical demonstrations to enhance nursing students' knowledge and preparedness for handling life-threatening emergencies.

emphasize the importance of incorporating structured BLS education and hands-on practice into the nursing curriculum to improve students' competence, confidence, and preparedness in managing life-threatening emergencies effectively. Strengthening BLS knowledge among nursing students can ultimately contribute to better patient outcomes and enhanced quality of care in clinical settings.

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